

A Comparative Computational Approach to Piano Modeling Analysis

Riccardo Simionato

Department of Musicology
University of Oslo

riccardo.simionato@imv.uio.no

Stefano Fasciani

Department of Musicology
University of Oslo

stefano.fasciani@imv.uio.no

ABSTRACT

Piano modeling is a topic of great interest in musical acoustics and sound synthesis. Besides challenges in modeling its mechanism, it is also difficult to understand how far the models are from the actual acoustic instrument and why. Identifying the most prominent aspects of the piano's sound and evaluating the sound-generation fidelity of associated models are usually addressed with studies based on listening tests. This paper shows how computational methods can provide novel insights into piano analysis and modeling, which can be used to complement perceptual analyses. In particular, our approach identifies audio descriptors that present discriminative differences between types of pianos when these are excited with specific stimuli. The proposed method is used to analyze a collection of recordings from upright acoustic and synthetic pianos, excited with single-played notes, triads, and repeated notes. Results show that the sound generated by the considered types of piano presents major differences in terms of spectral descriptors and constant-Q transform coefficients.

1. INTRODUCTION

The piano is a ubiquitous instrument in music. As well as other acoustic instruments, the piano presents unique timber not easily reproduced by their digital emulations. The piano characteristics are particularly challenging to imitate in computer simulations, especially when real-time and interactive sound synthesis is required. Nowadays, most commercial digital pianos are based on Pulse Code Modulation (PCM) synthesis, which requires a significant amount of memory to store pre-recorded audio samples, needed for the proper emulation of the instrument. In PCM-based synthetic pianos, keys are considered an isolated sound-generating mechanism, from which samples are independently recorded. Since piano keys are velocity-sensitive, recordings are taken for stimuli with different velocities, allowing the playback to emulate that the faster the key strike, the harder the hammer hits the strings. However, this is limited to a finite number of pre-recorded samples, resulting in a reduced variety of timbers against the possible stimuli velocity. PCM synthesis exploits interpo-

lation or mixing techniques when a particular example is missing from the pre-collected sample library. Thus, they emulate all the velocities starting from a pre-recorded subset of them, or similarly, they could interpolate adjacent notes (or cents) starting from pre-recorded ones. In addition, chords are played by summing the recording related to the notes composing them. In this case, the nonlinear mechanical coupling of simultaneously-played keys on the resulting sound would be missing. Indeed, the audible effect of simultaneous striking of different keys is not perceptual negligible [1]. Emulating this feature with PCM synthesis is not practically feasible because of the exponential growth in the number of recordings to be taken (at least one for each possible combination of stimuli) and the required dynamic memory size in the emulating device.

Another piano emulation approach is based on the physical description of the sound-generation process [2–4], which is still a subject of studies and investigations. Physics-based models, compared to PCM, do not require a large amount of memory but are computationally expensive because each audio sample is generated by solving a complex system of equations. This high computational demand can lead to inefficiency. Indeed most implementations of physics-based models rely on simplifying assumptions and approximations about the internal physics of the piano mechanism to lower its computational complexity. In addition, not all mechanical aspects of the piano are yet fully understood [5], resulting in challenges in considering all scenarios in which we can play the instrument. PCM-based and physics-based model implementations present a trade-off between computational cost and the emulation's accuracy.

When developing new models or improving the existing ones, it is critical to prioritize aspects to emulate with higher accuracy. The selection of these aspects should target those with a relevant audible result. Model evaluations assess how far the emulations are far from the acoustic instrument. For the specific case of the piano, standard practices are based on perceptual listening studies [6, 7]. Subjective human ratings of the emulated sound are the most common method in this context. They include the quality rating, identification of predominant characteristics of the sound, and relationship between perceptual evaluation and physical description. Subjective approaches help to validate the final models and to identify significant features that need to be emulated. However, they tend to be slow and require suitable subjects for the listening tests. In addition, the recording quality could affect the participant's

judgment. On the other hand, more objective evaluations are usually based on visual inspection of graphical representations of the signals and audio descriptors in the time or frequency domain. We recognize that there is a lack of numerical approaches to identify or highlight the differences between digital models and acoustic pianos, or more in general between different groups or categories of pianos. To this end, computational analysis techniques can be beneficial in finding more objective evaluation metrics to combine with perceptual tests and asserting the quality of a particular digital model. For example, the results of computational comparative analysis can inform the following perceptual investigations, allowing to focus on critical and relevant aspects of the specific model. Comparative techniques can be used as evaluators (also preliminary) for innovative modeling techniques and find out how close they are to the actual acoustic instrument and how they relate to other existing techniques. Computational approaches could also help to identify features that are most discriminative between acoustic devices and their digital counterparts, which can be further investigated to gain insights and improve the model’s accuracy.

Computational methods and machine learning are well-established for classification-related tasks [8, 9]. These methods have also been used for investigating tonality [10] and musical style evolution [11]. This paper further contributes to this research direction by proposing a computational approach to improve the understanding of how types of pianos differ from each other. The proposed method is applied to study how acoustic upright pianos differ from synthesized ones. The comparison between audio samples taken from different pianos (acoustic and digital) highlights which features may be more helpful to discriminate between different types of models. Our objective is to capture also nuances (or minor differences) that may be challenging to identify with listening tests, due to required experimental settings or weak relation with perceptive qualities. The comparison among acoustic and different modeling techniques is the most significant application of this comparative approach, but others are also possible, as discussed in the concluding section.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the computational method we propose for the comparative analysis of piano models, including audio descriptors, computation of stimuli-specific features, machine learning processing, and analysis of data. Section 3 describes the dataset we collected and used as a case study. Section 4 details the results of the proposed method applied to the dataset. Conclusions are included in Section 5.

2. COMPUTATIONAL COMPARATIVE METHOD

The assessment of the accuracy of a specific piano model is fairly straightforward in ideal conditions, which include the availability of the actual acoustic piano in an acoustic-treated room and with an electro-mechanical system to feed stimuli to the instrument, from which we can take recordings and compare them with the digital counterpart. If we scale this up, and we aim to make an assessment of how piano modeling techniques perform (i.e. identify

strengths and shortcomings in each modeling approach), we need the same above-described conditions for a large collection of pianos. Challenges emerge when seeking respective digital counterparts of acoustic pianos, as these are primarily commercial products with limited disclosed information. The comparative approach we propose here is sub-optimal but feasible, and it is not affected by the above-described practical challenges. Indeed, we initially compare each piano with itself, analyzing the dynamics of various audio descriptors when changing the input stimuli. This analysis is carried out on three groups of stimuli, single notes, triads, and repeated notes, over a dataset including recordings from a heterogeneous collection of pianos. For this study, we included acoustic, PCM-based, and physics-based models. We use machine learning techniques to cluster features from which we retrieve the most discriminative audio descriptors. Details on the proposed method are described in the following paragraphs and subsections. In Sec. 3, we detail the upright pianos we used in this study and how we created a mapping between MIDI velocity (used with the digital model) and finger pressures (used with acoustic pianos).

Our approach focuses on analyzing the dynamic variations and spectral changes at different pitches for a set of stimuli. In particular, we consider three types of stimuli: single note, triad (chord formed of three notes), and single repeated note (repetition of a single note). The latter two are representative of aspects that are critical but hard to model, such as the coupling between excited strings of different piano keys, and already-in-motion strings that are struck again. Therefore, for each piano considered in a comparative study and for each type of stimuli is necessary to record the sound generated with different velocities over the entire scale or a pitch range of interest.

2.1 Audio Descriptors

For this study, we compute an extensive set of audio descriptors: temporal centroid, the attack time (logarithmic), Constant-Q Transform (CQT) coefficients, Mel-Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCCs), Spectrum moments (mean, variance, skew, and kurtosis), spectral entropy, spectral contrast, spectral roll-off, spectral flux, spectral centroid, spectral energies, and harmonics magnitude. The descriptors are computed over a series of overlapping windows (size 23 ms and 50% overlap), from which we compute the mean, variance, skew, and kurtosis over the entire duration of the recording. For MFCC, CQT, and spectral contrast, which have more than one dimension, the mean is computed for each coefficient, frequency bin, and band, respectively.

The audio descriptors have been selected for the following reason. The temporal centroid is the balancing point in time of the sound event energy. The Logarithmic Attack Time is the time the signal takes to reach the max amplitude. Both descriptors indicate the onsets and envelopes variations of the sound, which could be helpful since the percussive-like nature of the instrument. Constant-Q Transform (CQT) describes the frequency domain of the sound as the Fourier transform but increasing time reso-

Feature Vector	Length
Δ Temporal Centroid	1
Δ Log Attack Time	1
Δ Constant-Q transform	72
<i>mean, variance, skew, kurtosis</i>	
Δ MFCCs	20
<i>mean, variance, skew, kurtosis</i>	
Δ Spectrum	1
<i>mean, variance, skew, kurtosis</i>	
Δ Spectral Entropy	1
Δ Spectral Contrast	7
<i>mean, variance, skew, kurtosis</i>	
Δ Spectral Roll-off	1
<i>mean, variance, skew, kurtosis</i>	
Δ Spectral Flux	1
<i>mean, variance, skew, kurtosis</i>	
Δ Spectral Centroid	1
<i>mean, variance, skew, kurtosis</i>	
Δ Spectral Energies	2
Δ First five harmonics magnitude	5
Velocity	1 or 2

Table 1. Features vector computed from the difference between the audio descriptors. A single velocity value is included for the triads and repeated-note stimuli, and two values for the single-note stimuli.

lution towards higher frequencies, resembling the situation in the human auditory system. Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) are based on a representation of the short-term power spectrum of a sound, where the frequency bands are spaced equally on the Mel-scale, which approximates the human auditory system’s response. CQT and MFCC give insights into how we perceive the frequency content of the piano notes. For this study, CQT is computed considering 72 frequency bins whereas MFCC is computed using 20 Mel-bands. Spectral mean, variance, skew, and kurtosis give statistical information about frequency distribution. Spectral skewness measures the symmetry of the spectrum around its arithmetic mean, while kurtosis measures the flatness, or non-Gaussianity, of the spectrum around its centroid. Spectral contrast considers the spectral peak, the spectral valley, and their difference in each frequency sub-band (6 in this case). Spectral entropy is a measure of uniformity of flatness. The latter descriptors, together with the first five harmonics magnitude, describe how the harmonics are excited by the hitting of the hammer. Spectral flux measures the spectral change between two successive frames, and it is a descriptor of the timber and onset of an audio signal. The spectral centroid indicates at which frequency the energy of a spectrum is centered and it is related to sound brightness and hence timber as well. Spectral roll-off is the frequency below which a specified percentage (85% in this case), of the total spectral energy, lies. It can indicate how the hammer excites the strings at different velocities. Finally, spectral energies similarly indicate how the frequency range closes to fundamental frequency, and the upper ones are

excited by the hammer nonlinearity [12]. Spectral energy audio descriptor is related to the fundamental frequencies of the collected notes. If f_{min} and f_{max} represent the minimum and maximum fundamental frequencies of the selected notes, respectively, the first spectral energy range will be $[f_{min} - \delta, f_{max} + \delta]$. δ is a manually selected parameter to consider harmonics close to the fundamental frequency. The other range considered will be $[f_{max} + \delta, -]$. A deeper and more detailed explanation of these descriptors is included in [13].

For the case of single-notes recording, we process the descriptors into feature vectors to be used with the machine learning algorithm, computing the differences between the descriptors for pairs of equal-pitch notes at different velocities. This is motivated by the focus of this comparative method, which is the extent to which descriptors change when changing the velocity of the single-note stimuli (rather than on their absolute value). The difference (i.e. the feature vector) is taken for each pair of equal-pitch and velocity-adjacent recordings in a dataset. Therefore with N recordings of a given note with different velocities, we generate $N - 1$ feature vectors. The absolute values of the two velocities are also included in the feature vector because the relative change in the descriptor, due to the nonlinear sound-generating process, does not only depend on the distance between the velocities. Each feature vector, as shown in Tab. 1, represents the descriptor difference (represented by the delta symbol) for an arbitrary velocity increase for a particular pitch of a given piano. The dimensionality of the feature vector is 423.

Similarly, for triad and repeated-note stimuli, we use the same set of descriptors, except for the harmonic magnitudes. For the triad stimuli, the feature vectors include the difference of the descriptors computed on the actual triad recording and on the sum of the single-note recordings composing the triad, representing the extent to which the model captures the nonlinear mechanical coupling of simultaneously-played keys. In this case, harmonics are not directly paired between the triads and the single notes in order to subtract them. For the repeated-note stimuli, the feature vector is composed of the difference between the descriptors computed on the single notes-recordings (i.e. played when the system was at rest) and the notes played with already-in-motion strings. Feature vectors for both triad and repeated notes are computed for all different velocity values. The obtained feature vector size is 417 for triads and 422 for repeated notes. In both, the velocity value is included in the feature vector.

2.2 Comparative Analysis

For each type of stimuli, we have a collection of feature vectors computed as previously described. Each feature vector is associated with a label representing the type of piano, acoustic or synthetic PCM-based or synthetic physics-based. For the single-note case, each vector is a high-dimensional representation of how the generated sound changes when increasing the velocity of the stimulus. For the triads and repeated notes, each vector represents how these are different from the simple sum (for triads) or se-

quencing (for repeated) of individually recorded notes.

The following processing steps are applied identically to each collection of feature vectors. First, feature vectors are normalized, scaling all components to zero mean and unitary variance. In this way, we have consolidated in a single vector heterogeneous descriptors with significantly different ranges. The normalized vectors and their labels are used to cluster the different types of pianos in separate regions of lower dimensional space. We use Linear Discriminant Analysis [14] (LDA) projection that maximizes the separability between the types of piano (acoustic, PCM, and physics), minimizing the within-type variance. LDA projects the feature vectors into a lower-dimensional space with dimensionality, or a number of components, equal to the number of classes minus one. We use the silhouette coefficient [15] to assess the extent to which data belonging to different groups of pianos are clustered in well-separated regions of the lower dimensional space. The silhouette coefficient, in our context, can assume values in the unitary range, where low values indicate overlap and high values indicate separated clusters, hence different stimuli-response across the different groups of pianos. When working with three or more groups, visually inspecting the LDA scatter plot of the feature vectors can provide further insights, such as the relative proximity (or overlap) between each pair of piano groups. On the other hand, full overlap in the scatter plot suggests no stimuli-response difference across the groups.

Since LDA components are linear combinations of individual features, we can further investigate which features are the most discriminative. We compute the correlation coefficient between each feature and LDA components to take the cumulative sum of their absolute value. These quantities represent an overall estimate of how discriminative each feature is across the piano groups (given that the associated clusters are not overlapping) and therefore inform further detailed investigation to improve the models. Two or more features showing a high correlation with LDA components are not necessarily uncorrelated between them. This process can be repeated starting from a reduced set of descriptors to further confirm that a subset that is poorly discriminative (i.e. overlapping clusters, similar behavior across groups), that a subset is highly discriminative (i.e. separated clusters, different behavior across groups), or that a subset is discriminative only between some groups (i.e. some separated and some overlapping clusters, different and similar behavior across group pairs).

3. PIANO DATASET

The methodology described in the previous section is used to compare several upright pianos we have included in a dataset. Grand and upright pianos categories can not be directly compared because they present significant differences in size, structure, mechanism, and soundboard. However, the same comparative methodology can be applied also to a dataset of grand pianos. We collected examples from nine upright pianos: three acoustics, three synthetics PCM-based, and three synthetics physics-based. The number and category of pianos included in the dataset

Figure 1. Setup used to record real pianos, including the microphone placed close to the piano without the covering and the FSR installed on a key.

were dictated by the available acoustic pianos for the study. In our facilities, we have access to three different acoustic upright pianos in reasonably acoustic-treated rooms. Therefore, to balance the dataset we selected only three models of synthetic upright piano for both PCM- and physics-based synthesis, although we have access to a larger collection of them. The acoustic upright pianos from which we recorded data are *Yamaha U3AS*, *Disklavier MX100A*, and *Schimmel Braunschweig*. For the synthetic pianos, we rendered three different models of PCM-based pianos and three different models of physics-based pianos using *Kontakt*¹ and *Pianoteq*², respectively.

3.1 Data Collection

For this study, we focused only on the central keyboard range of the piano, where hammers and harmonic generation are similar among the different notes. The lowest and highest octaves can present diverse harmonic characteristics: extreme registers are noisier and with different hammers' sizes (heavier for low and lighter for higher registers). This aspect can lead to contradicting or inconclusive results in a comparative study, including the notes from the entire piano range. Instead, independently analyzing and comparing each register (low, medium, high) is more appropriate. In particular, to collect single-note and repeated-note data, the following notes were used: A3, A4, C4, E4, C5, and E5. For the triads, we used A3min and A4min. These were recorded using different velocities in the range MIDI 30 to 90, for the case of single and repeated, and 30 to 70 for the triads. This is because higher and lower velocities are particularly difficult to be struck consistently by the human pianist. Regarding the synthetic pianos, we rendered three PCM-based upright pianos VST plugins (*Kontakt*) and three physics-based upright pianos VST plugins (*Pianoteq*) using a DAW. The sampling frequency of the

¹ <https://www.native-instruments.com/en/products/komplete/samplers/kontakt-7/>

² <https://www.modartt.com/pianoteq>

database is 44.1 kHz. All audio samples (from acoustic and synthetic pianos) were trimmed to 2 seconds. With the selected note range, the resulting spectral energy ranges described in Sec. 2.1 are [150-750] and [750-2200]. To record the acoustic pianos we used a MOTU M4³ audio interface connected to an Earthworks M50 measurement microphone.⁴ We removed the case covering the strings to record the acoustic pianos and placed the microphone a few centimeters away from the instrument strings. This allowed us to further reduce any adverse effect of the room acoustic on the recorded data.

Recording stimuli at different velocities on the Disklavier is feasible as per the synthetic piano. The Disklavier can be excited by its electro-mechanical actuators driven by MIDI. For the Yamaha and the Schimmel, we fitted a Force-Sensitive Resistor (FSR) on the excited key, which data is captured by a *Bela* board, as visible in Fig. 1. The procedure we used to map pressure readings to MIDI velocity is explained in Sec. 3.2. Since the Yamaha and the Schimmel are actuated by a human, absolute precision and consistency are not possible. Therefore, for each stimulus, we recorded a variety of trials with as many different values of velocities as possible, and we manually inspected the audio and sensor data to remove eventual recording errors. Audio recordings are aligned to stimuli in a DAW in order to automatically split the whole recording into single audio files. Finally, the entire database (recordings and renderings) was processed with a 2nd-order IIR Digital Butterworth low-pass and a high-pass filter with a cut-off frequency of 15 and 22000 Hz, respectively. The total number of examples was 530 for the case of single notes, 96 for triads, and 96 for repeated notes.

We computed the differences for all the available velocities. One critical aspect of recording acoustic pianos is the lack of precision in playing a note at a particular pressure/velocity. As we explain in Sec 3.2, we computed a map between analog pressures and MIDI velocities. But still, applying the exact pressure in order to have a specifically chosen velocity is not feasible. For this reason, we could not have rounded and precise velocity values. We manually selected the recordings for the acoustic pianos, carefully selecting notes with a max of $-/+5$ difference for the velocities. We rendered digital piano examples with not perfectly equal velocities to get a fair comparison.

3.2 Pressure mapping

To estimate the MIDI velocity from the recordings of the *Schimmel* and *Yamaha* pianos we derived a mapping from FSR readings to equivalent MIDI velocity using the *Disklavier*. In particular, we installed the FSR on different keys of the *Disklavier* (one at a time) and we recorded the MIDI and pressure data while an expert pianist manually excited the instrument with a broad range of velocities. *Disklaviers* are manufactured by Yamaha Corporation⁵ and present electro-mechanical sensors and actuators for

Figure 2. Setup used for collecting data to find the mapping between sensor reading and MIDI velocity. An expert pianist is striking a key of the *Disklavier* on which we installed an FSR. MIDI and FSR data are captured by the *Bela* board and audio interface visible on top of the piano.

Figure 3. Mapping between the finger pressures and the MIDI velocity. The blue dots are readings collected from pressure-velocity pairs and the orange line is the result of the linear regression.

capturing and reproducing MIDI data, which we recorded using the MOTU M4 interface connected to the MIDI output of the piano. The FSR used for this measurement is the Interlink Electronics FSR® 402 with a diameter of 13 mm⁶ with a linear response above 30 g. The sensor is integrated into a custom-made voltage-divider and interfaced to a *Bela*⁷ board, which continuously stores a wave file of the sensor data at audio rate and resolution. On the other hand, MIDI values are directly stored in a text file. Fig. 2 shows the setup. In order to avoid recording aftertouch-like pressures, the motion of the fingers has been quick, raising the finger immediately after the strike. As expected, the sensor signal generated by each finger strike is an impulse with a relatively steep rising and falling front. We computationally find the peak of each impulse and use the peak value as a velocity reference of the strikes. Once we

³ <https://motu.com/en-us/products/m-series/m4/>

⁴ <https://earthworksaudio.com/measurement-microphones/m30/>

⁵ <https://www.yamaha.com/>

⁶ <https://www.interlinkelectronics.com/fsr-400-series>

⁷ <https://bela.io/>

Figure 4. Projected feature vectors to 2D space using LDA for the case of single-note stimuli.

had the vector containing peak pressure values, we simply paired it with the sequence MIDI values read from the text file. Finally, once we obtained the pairs sensor-peaks versus MIDI velocity we used linear regression to generalize the mapping between these. Fig. 3 shows some sensor readings against the MIDI velocities and the mapping obtained by linear regression. Lastly, after computing the mapping but before collecting data, we used the Disklavier fitted with the FSR to verify that the pianist was able to strike a triad with nearly-equal velocity on all three keys. The complete dataset and code are available online ⁸.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The two-dimensional LDA projection of the feature vectors for the dataset single-note stimuli is displayed in the scatter plot of Fig. 4. Three well-separated and clearly distinguished clusters are visible in the figure. This suggests that with respect to (at least) some of the features used for this comparative analysis, the group of acoustic, PCM-based, and physics-based pianos presents a different behavior. This is also confirmed by the silhouette coefficient which is equal to 0.75. We can also notice how the PCM-based cluster is closer to the acoustic one than the physics-based one. PCM-based models play pre-recorded audio files of existing acoustic pianos, and for this reason, they are expected to have more similarities with each other.

Tab. 2 shows the sum of the absolute value of the correlation coefficients between the individual features and the two LDA components. These values are theoretically in the range $[0, 2]$, but since features won't have a high correlation with both LDA components, they are expected to be in the range $[0, 1]$. Among the most correlated features, spectral flux comes first. The fifth and fourth harmonics magnitudes are also significant. Interesting to note how their correlations are inversely related to the harmonic number, with the fundamental being the lowest. Similarly, the energy in the range above the fundamental is more discriminative than the energy around it. CQT coefficients

⁸ <https://github.com/RiccardoVib/piano-Modeling-Analysis>

Figure 5. Projected feature vectors to 2D space using LDA for the case of chords scenario.

Figure 6. Projected feature vectors to 2D space using LDA for the case of repeated notes scenario.

come next in the ranking. The spectrum's mean is the most correlated among moments, with correlation proportional to the moment's order. These results suggest that the spectral indicators are the most discriminative between the three considered types of piano models, and variations on the spectrum and on the energy are particularly critical. Time-domain features such as temporal centroid and log attack time are not significant in this context, as well as MFCCs, which show small correlation coefficients.

For the triads stimuli, the LDA projection of the features computed on the entire dataset is displayed in Fig. 5. Three different clusters are visible also in this case. However, these are less pronounced compared to the previous case, as the silhouette coefficient is 0.53. Tab. 2 shows the sum of the absolute value of the correlation coefficients of individual features with the LDA components. Generally, the data in the table shows higher correlation coefficients compared with the previous stimulus, and also with different discriminative features. The feature presenting the highest correlation is the spectrum kurtosis. Spectral flux presents a high correlation also in this case. Spectral centroid and roll-off follow in the ranking, suggesting that they are more discriminative in triads than in the single-notes case. CQT coefficients still present higher correlations than MFCCs.

Features	Σ Abs Corr Coef SN	Σ Abs Corr Coef TR	Σ Abs Corr Coef RN
Δ MFCCs (mean)	0.026 M: 0.054 (1), m: 0.005 (17)	0.161 M: 0.338 (19), m: 0.009 (8)	0.163 M: 0.316 (6), m: 0.057 (2)
Δ MFCCs (var)	0.031 M: 0.067 (14), m: 0.003 (6)	0.162 M: 0.269 (6), m: 0.036 (19)	0.165 M: 0.361 (7), m: 0.028 (18)
Δ MFCCs (skew)	0.113 M: 0.305 (3), m: 0.004 (12)	0.320 M: 0.685 (3), m: 0.059 (9)	0.244 M: 0.547 (8), 0.036 m: (15)
Δ MFCCs (kur)	0.071 M: 0.176 (2), m: 0.009 (8)	0.320 M: 0.581 (18), m: 0.037 (0)	0.245 M: 0.579 (19), m: 0.048 (13)
Δ CQT (mean)	0.232 M: 0.526 (31), m: 0.069 (10)	0.375 M: 0.814 (3), m: 0.046 (62)	0.265 M: 0.723 (11), m: 0.023 (42)
Δ CQT (var)	0.209 M: 0.484 (31), m: 0.028 (9)	0.331 M: 0.698 (11), m: 0.018 (52)	0.284 M: 0.826 (11), m: 0.050 (56)
Δ CQT (skew)	0.118 M: 0.313 (68) m: 0.029 (55)	0.288 M: 0.786 (33), m: 0.058 (2)	0.205 M: 0.576 (10), m: 0.015 (46)
Δ CQT (kurtosis)	0.095 M: 0.230 (68), m: 0.005 (44)	0.276 M: 0.697 (33), m: 0.035 (67)	0.202 M: 0.567 (10), m: 0.014 (64)
Δ Spec. Contrast (mean)	0.106 M: 0.188 (0), m: 0.025 (3)	0.364 M: 0.818 (0), m: 0.117 (1)	0.212 M: 0.348 (0), m: 0.019 (5)
Δ Spec. Contrast (var)	0.155 M: 0.275 (4), m: 0.088 (0)	0.340 M: 0.632 (6), m: 0.105 (0)	0.222 M: 0.446 (0), m: 0.043 (5)
Δ Spec. Contrast (skew)	0.147 M: 0.280 (4), m: 0.049 (6)	0.305 M: 0.434 (3), m: 0.142 (6)	0.161 M: 0.304 (5), m: 0.022 (0)
Δ Spec. Contrast (kurtosis)	0.082 M: 0.206 (4), m: 0.038 (0)	0.249 M: 0.500 (3), m: 0.082 (4)	0.162 M: 0.240 (1), m: 0.111 (4)
Δ Temporal Centroid	0.048	0.309	0.166
Δ Log Attack Time	0.094	0.184	0.376
Δ Spectral Flux (mean)	0.502	0.510	0.202
Δ Spectral Flux (var)	0.464	0.671	0.266
Δ Spectral Flux (skew)	0.117	0.364	0.112
Δ Spectral Flux (kurtosis)	0.101	0.730	0.110
Δ Spectrum Mean	0.223	0.332	0.020
Δ Spectrum Variance	0.196	0.199	0.313
Δ Spectrum Skew	0.184	0.156	0.282
Δ Spectrum Kurtosis	0.185	0.819	0.035
Δ Spectral Energy (f_0)	0.203	0.330	0.147
Δ Spectral Energy ($> f_0$)	0.260	0.221	0.239
Δ Spectral Entropy	0.186	0.253	0.304
Δ Spec. Roll-off (mean)	0.098	0.485	0.433
Δ Spec. Roll-off (var)	0.050	0.453	0.210
Δ Spec. Roll-off (skew)	0.103	0.250	0.420
Δ Spec. Roll-off (kurtosis)	0.069	0.047	0.056
Δ Spec. Centroid (mean)	0.127	0.637	0.458
Δ Spec. Centroid (var)	0.057	0.747	0.310
Δ Spec. Centroid (skew)	0.091	0.364	0.151
Δ Spec. Centroid (kurtosis)	0.028	0.073	0.161
Δ Fundamental magnitudes	0.113	-	-
Δ 2 nd harmonic magnitudes	0.164	-	-
Δ 3 rd harmonic magnitudes	0.168	-	-
Δ 4 th harmonic magnitudes	0.270	-	-
Δ 5 th harmonic magnitudes	0.304	-	-

Table 2. Sum of the absolute value of correlation coefficients between the individual features and LDA components for all three considered cases: single-notes (SN), triads (TR), and repeated notes (RN). For non-scalar audio descriptors, the correlation is computed for all the samples composing them, but the table includes only their correlation mean, the maximum (M), and minimum (m) values with their relative index. The 10 features with the highest correlation are highlighted in gray and are the most discriminative among the piano groups considered in this study.

Time-domain features are again weaker than the rest.

Finally, Figs. 6 shows the LDA projection of the features for the repeated-note stimuli. Clusters are still visible, with a silhouette coefficient of 0.44. Correlation coefficients are detailed in Tab. 2. In this case, the spectral centroid is the feature with the highest correlation, following the spectral roll-off. This time, the attack time is particularly important, showing time-domain features being relevant in some cases. CQT coefficients are confirmed also, in this case, to be more discriminative than MFCCs.

5. CONCLUSION

We investigated how computational techniques can be used for analysis purposes in the context of modeling acoustic instruments such as the piano. We proposed a computational method to compare the sound produced by arbitrary groups of pianos across three types of stimuli. The method highlights if and to what extent the stimuli-response of a group is different than others and which are the most discriminative audio descriptors. We used this method to compare three groups of upright-type pianos: acoustic, synthetic PCM-based, and synthetic physics-based, for which we developed a custom dataset. The comparative study investigated three aspects: the variations of a large set of audio descriptors for different velocities of single-played notes, the difference between triads and the sum of the notes composing them, and the difference between a single note played with the system at rest and a single note played with the strings already in motion. The method indicates existing and consistent patterns in the sound generated by the different groups of pianos. Spectral audio descriptors are generally the most discriminative in our case study. Descriptors with a closer relationship with the human auditory system, such as the CQT, result in discrimination as well. Future studies, including computational psychoacoustic analysis and listening tests, can reveal how these features relate to audible results, also exploring the different perspectives that players may have compared to passive listeners. Although it is not trivial to find the relationship between discriminative audio descriptors and poorly-modeled nonlinear sound-generating mechanics in the piano, the results provided by this method can inform the further and deeper investigation of specific sonic aspects. Moreover, the proposed method can be used to evaluate novel approaches to piano synthesis at the early development stage when the sound quality is not yet at the level of well-established emulation techniques. This is because the method is based on intra-piano descriptor differences rather than inter-piano descriptor comparison. With an appropriate and larger dataset, including a more comprehensive collection of pianos arranged in appropriate groups, the method can suggest where a novel synthesis approach is placed with respect to the cluster of existing models.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] G. Weinreich, "Coupled piano strings," *The J. of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 62, no. 6, pp. 1474–1484, 1977.
- [2] N. Giordano and M. Jiang, "Physical modeling of the piano," *EURASIP J. on Advances in Signal Processing*, vol. 2004, no. 7, pp. 1–8, 2004.
- [3] B. Bank, S. Zambon, and F. Fontana, "A modal-based real-time piano synthesizer," *IEEE transactions on audio, speech, and language processing*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 809–821, 2010.
- [4] M. Ducceschi and S. Bilbao, "A physical model for the prepared piano," *Proc. 26th Int. Cong. of Sound Vib.(ICSV 2019), Montreal, Canada*, 2019.
- [5] J. Chabassier, A. Chaigne, and P. Joly, "Modeling and simulation of a grand piano," *The J. of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 134, no. 1, pp. 648–665, 2013.
- [6] J. Bensa, D. Dubois, R. Kronland-Martinet, and S. Ystad, "Perceptive and cognitive evaluation of a piano synthesis model," in *Int. Symposium on Computer Music Modeling and Retrieval*. Springer, 2005, pp. 232–245.
- [7] A. Osses Vecchi, A. Kohlrausch, and A. Chaigne, "Perceptual similarity between piano notes: Experimental method applicable to reverberant and non-reverberant sounds," *The J. of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 146, no. 2, pp. 1024–1035, 2019.
- [8] P. Mahana and G. Singh, "Comparative analysis of machine learning algorithms for audio signals classification," *Int. J. of Computer Science and Network Security (IJCSNS)*, vol. 15, no. 6, p. 49, 2015.
- [9] S. Zhang, O. Jafari, and P. Nagarkar, "A survey on machine learning techniques for auto labeling of video, audio, and text data," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2109.03784*, 2021.
- [10] C. Weiss and M. Müller, "Tonal complexity features for style classification of classical music," in *2015 IEEE Int. Conf. on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 688–692.
- [11] C. Weiß, M. Mauch, S. Dixon, and M. Müller, "Investigating style evolution of western classical music: A computational approach," *Musicae Scientiae*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 486–507, 2019.
- [12] D. Russell and T. Rossing, "Testing the nonlinearity of piano hammers using residual shock spectra," *Acta Acustica United with Acustica*, vol. 84, no. 5, pp. 967–975, 1998.
- [13] G. Sharma, K. Umapathy, and S. Krishnan, "Trends in audio signal feature extraction methods," *Applied Acoustics*, vol. 158, p. 107020, 2020.
- [14] R. A. Fisher, "The use of multiple measurements in taxonomic problems," *Annals of eugenics*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 179–188, 1936.
- [15] P. J. Rousseeuw, "Silhouettes: a graphical aid to the interpretation and validation of cluster analysis," *J. of computational and applied mathematics*, vol. 20, pp. 53–65, 1987.